

Technical Assistance In Documentation And Updating Of Instructive Supported In The “S.M.E.D”. System for the Format Change in the Packaging Line of the Industria Licorera Del Cauca

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The purpose of this work was to write the instructions to implement the methodology "SMED - Single Minute Exchange of Die" in the changes of formats of the bottling process in the "Industria Licorera del Cauca", supported by the model of the international standard of automation ISA S88; Likewise, the corresponding checklists were produced that provided information and control was made with the intention of guaranteeing the success of the project in the long term, for the development of this project involved all maintenance staff and process leaders. In addition, the 5'S technique was implemented in the mechanical maintenance area, where the ideal environmental conditions of work were created, resulting in a reduction of the time for the enlistment of work elements and parts for a more effective format change, minimizing time Unproductive for the productive process.

Keywords

S.M.E.D, Productivity, Format:

Biography

Nora F.Arciniegas. Industrial engineering student from fundación universitaria de Popayán.

Diego F. Espinosa Industrial engineering, is currently a fulltime teacher of the program of industrial engineering of the fundación universitaria de Popayán. Belongs to the investigation group IP (Innovation and productivity) with 5 years of experience in working with times and methods and movements, production, logistics.

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